

Influence of Leadership Style on Employees' Satisfaction in Food Establishments in Kabacan, Cotabato

Ronald P. Mangali Jr. ¹, Melchie G. Palapar, DM ¹, Apple R. Ureta, PhD ¹

¹ – College of Human Ecology and Food Sciences, University of Southern Mindanao, Kabacan Main Campus, Poblacion Kabacan, Cotabato

Publication Date: June 23, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15782226

Abstract

The study titled Influence of Leadership Style on Employees' Satisfaction in Food Establishments in Kabacan, Cotabato, aimed to describe the socio-demographic profile of respondents, assess the effectiveness of leadership styles, determine employees' satisfaction levels, examine the relationship between leadership style and satisfaction, and evaluate leadership style's influence on satisfaction. The study surveyed 50 employees in food establishments using a complete enumeration method and a structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, Spearman rho correlation, and simple linear regression.

Results revealed that most respondents were equal male and female, aged 20-35 years old, Ilocano, high-school graduates, working as food servers, with nearly three years of service. Leadership effectiveness varied across styles. Autocratic leadership was perceived as highly effective, providing structure and discipline. Democratic leadership helped define company

vision and mission, enhancing clarity and engagement. Transformational leadership was deemed highly effective, fostering an environment of insightfulness and innovation.

Employees reported very high satisfaction levels, particularly appreciating job stability and growth opportunities. A significant positive correlation was observed between leadership style and satisfaction, indicating that leadership plays a significant role in shaping workplace experiences. Further analysis demonstrated that leadership style significantly predicts employees' satisfaction.

The study highlights the importance of adopting appropriate leadership approaches to enhance employee morale, engagement, and retention in the food service industry. Understanding which leadership styles resonate most with employees can help managers create supportive and motivating workplaces, ultimately benefiting both employees and organizations.

Keywords: *Employee, Employees' Satisfaction, Food Establishments, Leadership Style, Managers, Relationship*

Introduction

One of the key instruments for inspiring workers and raising job satisfaction is leadership style. When discussing managers and their leadership style, the first thing that springs to mind is what managers do. The company or organization needs its employees to be satisfied. A satisfied employee is not only more likely to stay with the company, but he also serves as ambassador for the brand internally and externally. Moreover, satisfied employee can prevent customer dissatisfaction. Customer dissatisfaction happens when clients express their dissatisfaction with a business, product, or services. It's critical for businesses to quickly resolve consumer complaints in order to preserve the good name and avoid a detrimental effect on the marketing and sales initiatives.

The general objective of the study was to determine the influence and the relationship of leadership styles in selected food establishment and the satisfaction perceived by the employees. Specifically, it aimed to describe the socio- demographic profile of the respondents in the food establishments in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, tribe, years worked with the company and current position; to determine the level of effectiveness of leadership style as perceived by the employees in food establishment; to determine the level of employees' satisfaction in the food establishment; to determine the relationship between the level of effectiveness of leadership style and level of employees' satisfaction; and to determine the influence of leadership style on employees' satisfaction

This study investigates whether leadership style has a significant influence on employee satisfaction. It predicts that different leadership styles may affect how satisfied employees feel at work. The research tests if there is no significant relationship or influence. It also considers the possibility that leadership style truly affect satisfaction.

This study was conducted at the Municipality of Kabacan, North Cotabato from November 2024 to December 2024 in 10 selected food establishments. The study utilized the two-factor theory developed by Frederick Herzberg (1959). The two-factor theory focuses on employee motivation, explains why workers are dissatisfied with their jobs and what makes them happy. This relates to what is known as "hygiene factors," which include pay and working conditions. This facet pertains to prospects for development, responsibility, and acknowledgement.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive-correlational design was employed to describe variables in detail and look into their relationships without suggesting that one variable that caused another. The design is applicable in this study to determine the characteristics of population or group, to determine the socio-demographic profile of the respondent such as sex, age, highest educational attainment, years in the company, current position and tribe. Moreover, it is appropriate to use the correlational design because it deals to examine the relationship of leadership style and employees' satisfaction and simple linear regression was utilized to examine the influence of leadership style on employees' satisfaction.

Respondents

A total of 50 employees of legal age and work in food establishments in Kabacan, Cotabato served as respondents of the study.

Sampling Procedure

To determine the population, a complete enumeration was utilized. It means that the respondents of the study are all employees in the selected food establishments in Kabacan, Cotabato.

Research Instrument

The research instrument in this study was adopted from the research study entitled, Impact of Leadership Styles on Employee Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment by Nidadhavolu (2018). However, it was modified by the researcher. To gather the data, a questionnaire was administered and consisted of three parts in which part I: the socio-demographic profile of the respondent; part II the level of effectiveness of leadership style as perceived by the employees, and Part III the level of employees' satisfaction. The instrument was validated by the experts from the faculty of Department of Hospitality Management and one professional residing in Kabacan, Cotabato. After which, the research instrument was then piloted to test its reliability. The pilot testing in the first part of the research questionnaire obtained cronbach alpha coefficients of 0.830, 0.86, 0.937. This means that the Coefficient results are higher than 0.7 therefore, instruments are considered valid and reliable.

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection procedures are presented as follows:

A letter for each food establishment has been prepared to approval for the conduct of the study. Along with the letter of approval, the questionnaire was administered to employees of the food establishments.

The respondents were briefed in the purpose of the study and the contents of the questionnaire. They were assumed that their responses are kept confidential. An informed consent was also explained to get its approval. Administration of the questionnaire followed. After the retrieved, the data were collected, tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis.

Data Analysis Procedure

Frequency counts, percentages, mean, and Spearman Rho were employed to address the study's objectives. These statistical methods provided insight into the effectiveness of leadership styles and their relationship with employee satisfaction. The analysis aimed to evaluate leadership approaches within food establishments and their impact on workforce engagement and job fulfillment.

To assess leadership effectiveness, a rating scale was used, ranging from "Very Effective" (4.21 - 5.00) to "Very Ineffective" (1.00 - 1.80). Similarly, employee satisfaction was measured using a scale from "Very Satisfied" (4.21 - 5.00) to "Very Dissatisfied" (1.00 - 1.80). These scales allowed for a structured evaluation of managerial influence and employee well-being.

Spearman Rho correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between leadership effectiveness and employee satisfaction. The correlation values ranged from Perfect Positive Correlation (0.9 – 1.0) to Perfect Negative Correlation (-0.9 – -1.0), indicating varying degrees of association between leadership style and workforce morale. A strong positive correlation suggests that effective leadership contributes to higher employee satisfaction.

To determine the extent of leadership influence, simple linear regression was utilized. This statistical approach measured how leadership styles impact employee satisfaction, identifying whether leadership practices significantly affect workplace morale and productivity. The findings reinforce the importance of adopting suitable leadership strategies to foster a more engaged and motivated workforce.

To determine the influence of leadership style on employees' satisfaction, simple linear regression is used. Where it helps in determining whether the independent variable (leadership styles) and the dependent variable (employee satisfaction) are significantly correlated. It is able to measure leadership approach affect employees' satisfaction.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were carefully observed throughout the study, ensuring compliance with research standards for both employees and food establishment managers. The research proposal underwent ethical review by the University Research Ethics Committee, with clearance issued after one week. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, with informed consent obtained from owners and managers following approval of the data collection request. Respondents were fully briefed on the study's objectives, procedures, and the confidentiality of their responses.

The research instrument included an informed consent section, which respondents were instructed to review before signing. No known risks were associated with data collection, and confidentiality was strictly maintained. Identifying details such as employees' names, as well as those of owners and managers, were kept private throughout the study. This approach ensured ethical integrity and protected participant privacy while allowing for reliable data collection.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic profile of the respondents

This section presents the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, which includes their sex, age group, educational attainment, length of service in the company, current position, and tribal affiliation.

Table 1. Socio-demographic profile of the respondents

<i>CHARACTERISTICS</i>	<i>FREQUENCY (n=50)</i>	<i>PERCENTAGE</i>
<i>Sex</i>		
<i>Male</i>	25	50
<i>Female</i>	25	50
<i>Age</i>		
<i>18-20 years</i>	9	18

<i>20-26 years</i>	20	40
<i>26-35 years</i>	20	40
<i>35-46 years</i>	1	2
<i>High School</i>	22	44
<i>Bachelor's Degree</i>	19	38
<i>Master's Degree</i>	9	18
<i>Years of Working in the Company</i>		
<i>less than 6 months</i>	8	16
<i>6 months – 1 year</i>	13	26
<i>1-3 years</i>	17	34
<i>3-6 years</i>	6	12
<i>More than 6 years</i>	6	12
<i>Current Position</i>		
<i>Cashier/Reception</i>	9	18
<i>Food Server</i>	26	52
<i>Cook</i>	10	20
<i>House Keeping</i>	1	2
<i>Utility</i>	2	4
<i>Others; please specify</i>	2	4
<i>Tribe</i>		
<i>Ilocano</i>	21	42
<i>Ilonggo</i>	9	18
<i>Cebuano</i>	17	34
<i>Maguindanaon</i>	3	6

The study revealed an equal sex distribution, highlighting the significance of gender balance in leadership dynamics. Most respondents were between 20-35 years old, with younger employees potentially perceiving leadership effectiveness differently.

Educational attainment varied, with a majority being high school graduates and a minority holding college degrees, influencing workplace expectations and responses to leadership styles. Tenure in the company ranged from one to three years, with newer employees benefiting from supportive leadership approaches.

Food servers comprised the largest job category, making leadership's role in fostering communication and service quality essential. Additionally, the majority of respondents were Ilocano, suggesting that cultural values such as diligence and perseverance shape leadership preferences.

Generally, leadership strategies that account for these socio-demographic factors can enhance employee satisfaction, engagement, and retention.

Effectiveness of leadership style perceived by the employees in food establishments.

Table 2 examines the level of effectiveness of leadership styles as perceived by employees in food establishments in Kabacan, Cotabato.

Table 2. The level of effectiveness of leadership style that is perceived by the employees in food establishments in Kabacan, Cotabato

STATEMENTS	WEIGHTED MEAN	VERBAL DESCRIPTION
Autocratic Leadership Style		
1. Manager makes most of the decisions without consulting the team.	3.56	Effective
2. Manager closely monitors all aspects of work.	4.18	Effective
3. Manager's control leads to higher efficiency in task completion.	4.36	Very effective
4. Leadership style hinders creative and innovative thinking.	4.42	Very Effective
5. Leadership can cope high-pressure job or even under critical conditions.	4.36	Very Effective
Sub Mean:	4.18	Effective
Democratic Leadership Style		
6. Transparency leads to a good decision-making process with your manager.	4.62	Very Effective
7. Encourage to share ideas and opinions on work-related matters.	4.58	Very Effective
8. Leadership clearly defines mission and vision of the company.	4.72	Very Effective
9. Leadership has positively impacted work experience.	4.40	Very Effective
10. Leadership approach to better support employee's involvement.	4.62	Very Effective
Sub Mean:	4.59	Very Effective
Transformational Leadership Style		
11. Manager promotes an atmosphere of teamwork.	4.50	Very Effective
12. Manager listens to team member's point of views before taking decisions	4.52	Very Effective
13. Manager appreciates accomplishments.	4.52	Very Effective
14. Manager gives insightful suggestions on how the job should be done.	4.62	Very Effective
15. Manager makes decisions that promote team's performance and productivity.	4.58	Very Effective
Sub Mean:	4.55	Very Effective

OVERALL MEAN	4.44	Very Effective
---------------------	-------------	-----------------------

*Legend: 4.21-5.0-very Effective; 3.41-4.20-Effective; 2.61-3.40- Neither Effective nor Ineffective;
1.81-2.60- Ineffective; 1.00-1.80- Very Ineffective*

The study evaluated three distinct leadership styles—autocratic, democratic, and transformational—to determine their effectiveness in food establishments. Autocratic leadership, which prioritizes control and decision-making by the leader, had a weighted mean of 4.42, indicating that it was perceived as highly effective in maintaining structure but potentially limiting creativity and innovation. This leadership style ensures efficiency in task completion but may negatively impact employee morale, leading to lower motivation and potential turnover. Democratic leadership, on the other hand, received the highest effectiveness rating of 4.72, emphasizing its strength in defining a company’s mission and vision. Employees responded positively to managers who encouraged collaboration, though democratic leadership also introduced challenges, such as group conflicts that could affect workplace cohesion.

Transformational leadership was also highly rated, with a weighted mean of 4.62, particularly for managers who provided insightful suggestions and fostered a proactive work environment. This style promotes employee empowerment, motivation, and engagement, contributing to long-term success. Establishing a team atmosphere enhances employee productivity and satisfaction, reinforcing the importance of interpersonal connections within organizations. The overall leadership effectiveness mean was 4.04, affirming that strong leadership skills are critical for influencing workplace performance. The study supports previous research indicating that leadership styles are not fixed but can be developed over time, allowing managers to adapt their approaches based on situational needs and employee characteristics to achieve sustainable organizational growth.

Level of the employees’ satisfaction in the food and beverage establishment in Kabacan, Cotabato

Table 3 presents the level of the employees’ satisfaction in the food establishment in Kabacan, Cotabato.

Table 3. The level of the employees’ satisfaction in the food establishments in Kabacan, Cotabato

CHARACTERISTICS	WEIGHTED MEAN	VERBAL DESCRIPTION
<i>Employees’ Satisfaction</i>		
1. I am given the chance to do multiple things associated with the projects assigned.	4.38	Very Satisfied
2. I am satisfied for the opportunity that this job provides for steady growth.	4.64	Very Satisfied
3. I am satisfied with the job subjected to favorable working conditions.	4.54	Very Satisfied
4. I am satisfied with my skills thoroughly utilized in my job.	4.52	Very Satisfied
5. I am satisfied doing the work diligently and initiatively.	4.58	Very Satisfied

6. I am satisfied with the company that gives fair opportunities for promotions and career growth.	4.50	Very Satisfied
7. I am satisfied with any kind of job responsibilities assigned to me	4.58	Very Satisfied
8. I am satisfied of having excellent place of work.	4.52	Very Satisfied
9. I am satisfied and delighted to spend the rest of my career with this company	4.46	Very Satisfied
10. I am satisfied and confident to continue working with my current employer	4.48	Very Satisfied
OVERALL MEAN	4.52	Very Satisfied

Legend: 4.21-5.0-very satisfied; 3.41-4.20-satisfied; 2.61-3.40- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied;

1.81-2.60- dissatisfied; 1.00-1.80- Very dissatisfied

The study results indicate that employees in food establishments in Kabacan, Cotabato are highly satisfied with the growth opportunities their jobs provide, with an overall mean of 4.52, categorized as "Very Satisfied." Employee satisfaction plays a crucial role in workplace dynamics, as it fosters loyalty, motivation, and commitment, leading to enhanced productivity and reduced turnover rates. Satisfied employees take pride in their roles, contribute meaningfully to organizational goals, and positively impact service delivery. Research further highlights that a favorable quality of work life is essential in shaping employee satisfaction, reinforcing the importance of a supportive work environment that meets employees' needs.

Despite the high satisfaction levels, multitasking was identified as a potential challenge, with employees experiencing productivity declines due to task overload. Management strategies, such as encouraging employees to focus on one task at a time, conducting training sessions, and fostering clear communication, can help mitigate these issues and improve work efficiency. Organizations that prioritize employee recognition, participation, and flexibility create more positive workplace experiences, further reinforcing job satisfaction. Ultimately, employee empowerment and strong leadership contribute to sustainable workplace success and professional growth, benefiting both employees and the organization.

The relationship between the level of effectiveness of leadership style and level of employees' satisfaction

As shown in the Table 4, the relationship between the perceived effectiveness of leadership styles and the level of employee satisfaction in food establishments in Kabacan, Cotabato is highlighted.

Table 4. The relationship between the level of effectiveness of leadership style and level of employees' satisfaction in the food establishment in Kabacan, Cotabato

VARIABLE	CORRELATION COEFFICIENT	p-value	Decision
Leadership Style-	0.834	<.001	Reject Ho

 Level of Employees'
 Satisfaction

*Legend:**Ranges of Correlation*

-0.9 - -1.0

-0.7 - -0.9

-0.5 - -0.7

0 - 0.5

0.5 - 0.7

0.7 - 0.9

0.9 - 1.0

*Strength of Relationship**Perfect Negative Correlation**High Negative Correlation**Low Negative Correlation**No Correlation**Low Positive Correlation**High Positive Correlation**Perfect Positive Correlation*

The study confirms a strong positive correlation between leadership style effectiveness and employee satisfaction, with a Spearman rho value of 0.834, indicating that leadership approaches significantly shape workplace dynamics. Leaders influence employee attitudes and behaviors through their communication, decision-making, and interactions, either fostering a productive environment or hindering professional growth. Different leadership styles—Autocratic, Democratic, and Transformational—vary in their approach, but all share fundamental principles that define leadership effectiveness.

Effective leaders demonstrate flexibility, guiding employees while encouraging creativity and initiative, whereas ineffective leaders focus solely on achieving specific goals. The study's findings support the hypothesis that leadership style plays a crucial role in employee satisfaction, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis that no significant relationship exists between the two.

The influence of effectiveness of leadership style on employees' satisfaction

Table 5 disclosed the degree of influence of the effectiveness of the leadership style on employees' satisfaction.

Table 5. Model Summary for Employees' Satisfaction

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
	Leadership Style	.494			
R					
R²	.839				
Adjusted R²	.704				
Durbin-Watson	.698				
	2.289				

Dependent Variable: *Employee Satisfaction*

Significant: * $\alpha = 0.05$, ** $\alpha = 0.01$

The study disclosed a strong positive correlation between leadership styles and employee satisfaction, with an R value of 0.839, indicating that leadership approaches significantly impact workplace morale and productivity. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.704$) suggests that leadership styles account for 70% of employee satisfaction, reinforcing their critical role in shaping workplace dynamics. The adjusted R^2 value of 0.698 confirms the model's reliability, with minimal shrinkage, ensuring its applicability beyond the sample population. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.289 indicates non-autocorrelation, validating the independence of variables in explaining employee satisfaction. Leadership styles were found to be significant predictors of employee satisfaction, with a p-value of <0.001 , emphasizing their influence on workplace engagement, retention, and overall organizational success. Effective leadership fosters motivation, commitment, and collaboration, while poor leadership can lead to decreased morale and higher turnover rates. The study ultimately rejects the null hypothesis, affirming that leadership styles play a crucial role in employee satisfaction and workplace effectiveness.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The following conclusions are drawn.

1. Most respondents are male and female aged 20-35, Ilocano's, high school graduate, food servers and working in the company from 1-3 years.
2. The level of effectiveness of leadership style perceived by the employees in food establishments in terms of autocratic leadership style that managers who only hinder creative innovative thinking are very effective for the employees. In democratic leadership style, it is very effective for the employees when managers' leadership tend to define the company's mission and vision, clearly. While in transformational leadership style, it is also very effective for the employees when managers cultivate an atmosphere of insightfulness can help employees be more insightful and proactive. Democratic leadership style received the highest percentage that described very effective.
3. The level of the employees' satisfaction in the food establishments in Kabacan, Cotabato is very satisfied with the opportunity their job provides for steady growth.
4. The study also concludes that leadership style and employees' satisfaction have a high positive correlation.
5. The influence of leaderships style are significant predictor in determining employee satisfaction.

The following are the recommendations based on the findings and conclusions of the study.

1. Training for leadership style within food establishments is highly recommended particularly on training programs in food establishments. How well these programs prepare leaders in their leadership techniques and whether they positively affect employee satisfaction, retention, and overall organizational performance.
2. Look how leaders' emotional intelligence influences leadership style and engagement with employees' satisfaction, manage conflict, and boost morale among employees' who are not emotionally attuned.
3. Further study could explore how different leadership styles influence the quality of service of employees provide to customers, if that meets and improve service standards that could offer insight to customer satisfaction.
4. Future research could aim to include a wider variety of job roles, such as kitchen staff, managers, or other support staff. Each group may have a different perception of leadership and including a more diverse range of roles will provide a more holistic view of how leadership styles impact satisfaction across the organization.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, N., & Wahab, J. L. A. (2023). Principal Autocratic Leadership Practice and its Relationship with Teacher Job Satisfaction in Secondary Schools of Jempol District, Negeri Sembilan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 13(9). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v13-i9/18637>
- Afsar, B. (2014). Moral or Authoritative Leadership: Which One is Better for Faculty Members? *American Journal of Educational Research*, 2(9), 793–800. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-2-9-14>
- ANNEKE KUIJK. (2018, February 20). *Two Factor Theory of Motivation by Frederick Herzberg | ToolsHero*. Toolshero. <https://www.toolshero.com/psychology/two-factor-theory-herzberg/>
- Akor. (2020). Akor, P. U. (2014). *Influence of Autocratic Leadership Style on the Job Performance of Academic Librarians in Benue State*. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 4, 148-152. - References - Scientific Research Publishing. Scirp.org. [https://www.scirp.org/\(S\(czeh4tfqyw2orz553k1w0r45\)\)/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2875633](https://www.scirp.org/(S(czeh4tfqyw2orz553k1w0r45))/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2875633)
- Amini, M. Y., Mulavizada, S., & Nikzad, H. (2019). The impact of autocratic, democratic and laissez-fair leadership style on employee motivation and commitment: a case study of Afghan wireless communication company (Awcc). *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 21(6), 45-50.
- BambooHR. (2023). *What is job dissatisfaction?* | BambooHR. www.bamboohr.com
- Barney, N. (2023, March). *What is leadership?* TechTarget. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchcio/definition/leadership>
- Bathena, Z. (2018). *Why job satisfaction is so important for an Employee*. Entrepreneur. <https://www.entrepreneur.com/en-in/growthstrategies/why-job-satisfaction-is-so-important-for-an-employee/310608>
- Bauer, T., & Erdogan, D. (2011). (PDF) *Organizational socialization: The Effective on boarding of new employees*. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/285000696_Organizational_socialization_The_effective_onboarding_of_new_employees
- Belias, D., & Koustelios, A. (2014). Leadership and job satisfaction--A review. *European Scientific Journal*, 10(8).
- Deeb, C. (2024). Multitasking effects on workers' performance. *Chron*.

<https://smallbusiness.chron.com/multitasking-effects-workers-performance-32339.html>

Brillo, & Boonstra. (2018). *Tri-intersectional Model of Leadership by Values (TMLV) Assessment – João Brillo*. Joaobrillo.com. https://joaobrillo.com/?page_id=82&lang=en

Field, A. (2009). *Field, A. (2009) Discovering Statistics Using SPSS. 3rd Edition, Sage Publications Ltd., London. - References – Scientific Research Publishing. Www.scirp.org.* <https://www.scirp.org/reference/ReferencesPapers?ReferenceID=1866193>

Frost, J. (2013). *How to interpret r-squared in regression analysis*. Statistics by Jim. <https://statisticsbyjim.com/regression/interpret-r-squaredregression/>

Ghasabeh, M. S., Soosay, C., & Reaiche, C. (2015). The emerging role of transformational leadership. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 49(6), 459– 467.

Kim, S., & Yoon, G. (2015b). An Innovation-Driven culture in local government. *Public Personnel Management*, 44(2), 147–168. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0091026014568896>

Kuranchie, M., & Amponsah-Tawiah, K. (2016). *Employee Motivation and Work Performance A Comparative Study of Mining Companies in Ghana. Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 9, 255-309. - References - Scientific Research Publishing. Scirp.org. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2682193>

Larsson, G., & Björklund, C. (2020). Age and leadership: comparisons of age groups in different kinds of work environment. *Management Research Review*, 44(5), 661–676. <https://doi.org/10.1108/mrr-01-20200040>

Lucas, R., & Deery, M. (2019). Significant developments and emerging issues in human resource management. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 23(5), 459–472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2004.10.005>

Muttalib, A., Danish, M., & Zehri, A. W. (2023). The impact of leadership styles on employee's job satisfaction. *Research Journal for Societal Issues*, 5(2), 133– 156. <https://doi.org/10.56976/rjsi.v5i2.91>

Pasamar, S., Diaz-Fernandez, M., & de la Rosa-Navarro, M. D. (2019). Human capital: the link between leadership and organizational learning. *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, 28(1), 25–51. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ejmbe-08-2017-0003>

- Peker, S. (2018). *The relationship between leadership styles (Autocratic and democratic) of school administrators and the mobbing teachers suffer.* (2018). *European Journal of Contemporary Education*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.13187/ejced.2018.1.150>
- Reyaz, N. S. (2024). The influence of leadership styles on employee motivation and job satisfaction. *Deleted Journal*, 2(03), 339–344.
<https://doi.org/10.47392/irjaem.2024.0049>
- Ricketts, D. (2020). *High School Graduates' Perspectives on Employment and Service Learning – ProQuest.* Proquest.com. <https://www.proquest.com/Openview/85407b0b350ec425272e1688a583dc19/1?cbl=51922&diss=y&pq-origsite=gscholar>
- Saffrudin, M., & Nohong, M. (2023, May 29). The Relationship of Leadership Style to Employee Performance: A Schematic Literature Review. www.atlantispress.com; Atlantis Press.
https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-146-3_69
- Saied, K. (2023, July 31). *The impact of leadership styles on employee satisfaction: A tale of two work environments.* www.linkedin.com.
<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/impact-leadershipstyles-employee-satisfaction-tale-kimberly/>
- Sethuraman, Kavitha, and Jayshree Suresh. “Effective Leadership Styles.” *International Business Research*, vol. 7, no. 9, 24 Aug. 2014, pp. 165172. pdfs.semanticscholar.org/d2a2/528ddffc694b43fd5bcf3c68826de4da2eb3.pdf,
<https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v7n9p165>.
- Tenney, M. (2024). How leadership affects organizational success. <https://businessleadershiptoday.com/how-does-leadership-affect-organizational-success/>
- Tremmel, M., & Wahl, I. (2023). Gender stereotypes in leadership: Analyzing the content and evaluation of stereotypes about typical, male, and female leaders. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14(14). [frontiersin.
https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1034258](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1034258)
- Ulberg, S. (2015, June 3). *11 Signs of ineffective leaders.* Business Training Experts. <https://businesstrainingexperts.com/eleven-signyouorganization-has-ineffective-leaders/>
- Viljoen, A, et al. “Understanding the Role That Quality of Work Life of Food and Beverage Employees Plays in Perceived Service Delivery and Productivity.” *Southern African Business Review*, vol. 18, no. 1, 24 Jan. 2019, p. 27, <https://doi.org/10.25159/1998-8125/5644>. Accessed 6 Apr. 2019.

Wikipedia Contributors. (2020, January 22). *Ilocano people*. Wikipedia; Wikimedia Foundation.
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ilocano_people